

An Innovative Approach to Web User-Experience (UX) Prototyping in the AI Era with Live DOM Editing Using Real-time Data

Samir Kumar Dash¹[0009-0007-8887-9265]

¹ Cisco Systems (India) Pvt. Ltd., Bengaluru, Karnataka, India
samdash@cisco.com

Abstract. In the AI era, prototyping web user experiences (UX) faces significant challenges, particularly when real-time data integration is essential. Traditional prototyping methods often fall short as they fail to accurately reflect user interactions in the absence of real data. Features that depend heavily on real data, such as personalized recommendations and data visualizations, are particularly challenging to prototype effectively without access to authentic datasets. Furthermore, with the increasing adoption of AI in web applications, the necessity for data-driven outcomes to be thoroughly tested during the prototyping phase has become paramount.

This research paper introduces a novel approach termed *Prototyping with Data-driven Live DOM Editing (ProDaLiDE)*. This innovative method leverages real-time data to enable dynamic and interactive modifications of the *Document Object Model (DOM)* during the prototyping stage, ensuring a more accurate representation of the final product. By integrating live data into the prototyping process, developers can create more realistic and responsive user experiences, validate AI-driven features, and optimize the design before full-scale implementation. This approach not only bridges the gap between concept and reality but also enhances the efficiency and effectiveness of UX prototyping in the AI-driven landscape.

Keywords: prototyping, user experience, ux, artificial intelligence, data, dom, html, web application.

1 Introduction

1.1 Current State of UX Prototyping for Web Applications

As AI has been evolving swiftly and making substantial contributions across domains in recent years, especially, the Generative AI holds opportunities to transform productivity across functions and industries (Singh, 2023). However, when it comes to see its impact in the design process involved in product innovation and solutioning, the web prototyping faces unprecedented challenges as enterprises rapidly adopt AI-related features to enhance their solutions, fundamentally transforming web applications and ecosystems (Daniel, 2024). The accelerated pace of AI evolution has led to widespread integration of AI, necessitating that user experience (UX) design extends beyond mere

creation of interaction touchpoints (Takaffoli et al., 2024). Modern UX prototyping must address personalization and the dynamic outcomes produced by AI algorithms, which are pivotal for delivering tailored and effective user experiences (Churchill and Sarma, 2014).

However, traditional prototyping methods often fall short, as they struggle to accurately reflect user interactions without real data. These conventional approaches lack the ability to simulate the nuanced and data-driven behaviors that AI-enhanced features demand, leading to prototypes that do not adequately represent the final product's functionality and user experience. Consequently, the need for innovative prototyping methods that incorporate real-time data and dynamic interactions is more critical than ever, ensuring that prototypes can effectively validate AI-driven features and provide a true representation of the user experience in AI-integrated web applications.

1.2 Goal of this paper

Our initial focus was to gain a comprehensive understanding of the challenges faced in traditional prototyping for data-driven and AI-enhanced web applications. Recognizing the complexities and limitations inherent in conventional prototyping methods, we set out to identify specific challenges that pose challenges to the effective representation and testing of dynamic data-driven features and real-time AI/ML interactions. Based on this our goal was also to determine if there are any effective techniques available that could bridge the gap between static prototypes and the dynamic, data-intensive nature of modern web applications and which would help to enable more accurate, efficient, and interactive prototyping processes, ultimately enhancing the development and user experience of AI-integrated web applications.

2 Observations & Hypothesis for the Experiment

2.1 Analyzing the prototypes created with traditional approach

To analyze the challenges and data quality issues in traditional prototyping for data-driven and AI-enhanced web applications, we conducted a thorough examination of twenty-four prototypes created using tools like *Figma*, *InVision*, *MS Powerpoint* and custom hand-coded HTML files, that were used in various Enterprise web application projects. Each prototype was carefully analyzed to list the number of data points (e.g. form fields, charts, data grid or table rows etc.), and how many of them were using static mock data leading to mismatches from the real context and data sets expected in requirement specs/ or in later implemented production app. Also, the list included the navigational dead-ends or missing/ broken links. Also, if the prototype was iterated post stake holder review sessions to make changes to the data fields were noted. These are listed in Table 1, in the following.

Table 1. Analyzing some prototypes created with static data.

Prototype	Prototyping Tool	Data Points (Fields/ labels/ table rows)	Data Mismatch / Missing Data Issues	% of data points impacted	Dead-end/ Broken/ Missing Links	Iterations on Prototype based on stakeholder's feedback
Prototype 1	Figma	131	14	10.69	2	1
Prototype 2	Figma	267	23	8.61	4	1
Prototype 3	Figma	113	7	6.19	1	0
Prototype 4	Figma	97	1	1.03	3	0
Prototype 5	Figma	493	4	0.81	0	0
Prototype 6	Custom HTML	339	22	6.49	0	1
Prototype 7	Figma	219	3	1.37	0	0
Prototype 8	Invision	25	0	0.00	3	0
Prototype 9	Invision	128	8	6.25	6	0
Prototype 10	Invision	112	3	2.68	1	0
Prototype 11	Figma	142	42	29.58	3	1
Prototype 12	Figma	764	21	2.75	4	0
Prototype 13	MS PowerPoint	651	65	9.98	14	1
Prototype 14	MS PowerPoint	669	73	10.91	13	1
Prototype 15	Figma	356	23	6.46	19	0
Prototype 16	Custom HTML	232	21	9.05	12	0
Prototype 17	Custom HTML	118	11	9.32	27	0
Prototype 18	Figma	97	1	1.03	12	0
Prototype 19	Invision	82	0	0.00	11	0
Prototype 20	Invision	65	3	4.62	12	0
Prototype 21	Invision	112	23	20.54	4	1
Prototype 22	Figma	129	12	9.30	7	0
Prototype 23	Figma	268	26	9.70	9	1
Prototype 24	MS PowerPoint	128	25	19.53	5	1

From the list, observations and patterns that emerge as following:

1. The medium sized prototypes with data points between 100-350 had a significant impact due to missing or mismatched data.
2. Majority of the time where the prototype is reworked due to not meeting the criteria for the stakeholder has significant number of data-points (i.e between 7% and 10%) with missed or mismatched data.

2.2 Solution Hypothesis

As HTML DOM requires the minimum amount of time and the smallest data footprint as compared to Regular Expression (RegEx) and XPath methods (Gunawan et al., 2019), it is an effective method of data scraping from a webpage. To simulate real-time data on the UI within the context of the data, inline DOM editing can significantly enhance the prototyping process. By enabling designers to make live modifications directly within the browser, this approach will allow for immediate visualization and testing of dynamic data interactions and AI-driven features. Utilizing backend technologies like PHP, Node.js, Python, and JSON, combined with HTML5 and JavaScript on the client-side, and for AI related features, integrating APIs like the OpenAI API models, it is hypothesized that inline DOM editing will provide a more accurate and responsive representation or simulation of the final product. This method is expected to streamline the design process, reduce iteration time, and improve the overall user experience by ensuring that prototypes reflect the true behavior and performance of the application in real-world scenarios, leading to a more refined and functional design.

2.3 Proposed System Design

To simulate real-time data on the UI within the context of the data, inline DOM editing can significantly help. The solution comprises two main components: a Chrome browser extension and a local server with backend script support, utilizing programming languages such as PHP, Python, or any other backend language. This architecture aims to provide a dynamic and interactive approach to web prototyping by leveraging real-time data manipulation and AI integration.

Fig. 1. The architecture of the *Prototyping with Data-driven Live DOM Editing (ProDaLiDE)*.

Execution Methodology: The proposed architecture effectively bridges the gap between static prototyping and dynamic, data-driven web applications. By utilizing a Chrome browser extension to inject a locally hosted JavaScript file, the solution enables real-time DOM manipulation, data gathering, and integration with backend AI services. This comprehensive approach not only enhances the fidelity of web prototypes but also streamlines the design and development process, providing a robust tool for modern web application prototyping.

This approach would allow the designer to simulate real user interactions and visualize dynamic data changes, providing stakeholders with a more interactive and accurate representation of the final product. This iterative process ensured that the prototype closely aligned with stakeholder expectations and facilitated rapid feedback and adjustments, ultimately leading to a more refined and functional design.

2.4 Process and Methodology Involved within UX Design Workflow

The proposed approach involves the typical UX design process, where the designer, based on the stakeholder requirements, initially creates a block-level low-fidelity concept using any wireframing tools e.g. Figma or Miro or any other applications. This preliminary stage involved outlining the essential layout and functional elements of the web application, focusing on user flow and interaction design without delving into detailed aesthetics.

Fig. 2. Showing the proposed methodology as part of typical UX design process.

2.4.1 Concept Design Phase: Once the stakeholders reviewed and approved the lofi concepts, the designer transitioned to a more dynamic prototyping phase using the proposed approach, i.e. *Prototyping with Data-driven Live DOM Editing (ProDaLiDE)*. With *ProDaLiDE* approach, the designer now could run the experiment of the hypothesis by enabling live edits to the DOM directly within the browser on the target application to create the dynamic prototype, injecting real-time data into the prototype.

2.4.2 Preparatory Assessment & Identification of Data: The key steps in the proposed In the experiment, the following steps are carried out to ensure that the required data is available for prototype creation.

Step 1 - Identify the Data Points Involved in Prototyping: Begin by outlining the key data points that are crucial for the prototype. These include all elements that will be dynamically updated or interacted with during user sessions. Examples of data

points might include user profiles, product details, real-time analytics, form inputs, and interactive charts.

Step 2 - Find Out and List the Data Elements Available on the Live Site: Navigate through the live site and document the pages where these data elements are located. Use browser developer tools to inspect the DOM structure and identify elements using `querySelector` or similar methods. Examples of selectors might include `document.querySelector('.user-profile')` for user profiles or `document.querySelectorAll('.product-item')` for product details.

Step 3 - Scan Data Elements Using querySelectors: Write scripts to scan the identified pages for the relevant data elements. Example script:

```
const userProfile = document.querySelector('.user-profile');
const productItems = document.querySelectorAll('.product-item');
```

Step 4 - Identify and List the Data Points in Other Views or Sources: Determine which data points are not present on the current view but are needed for a comprehensive prototype. These might include data from different user account views, administrative panels, or third-party APIs.

Step 5 - List the Data Sources: Catalog the various data sources, noting which are directly accessible from the current page and which are available from other views or external sources. Examples include internal databases, external APIs, and auxiliary pages that need to be loaded separately.

Step 6 - Load Data Sources in Hidden iframes: For data points located on other views or external sources, create hidden iframes to load these sources without disrupting the user experience. Example iframe integration:

```
<iframe id="data-source-frame" src="https://example.com/data-source" style="display:none;"></iframe>
```

Step 7 - Grab Data from iframes Using API Consumption: Access the data from the hidden iframes and integrate it into the main prototype. Use JavaScript to retrieve the iframe content and process the data as needed. For example:

```
const iframe = document.getElementById('data-source-frame');
iframe.onload = function() {
  const iframeDocument = iframe.contentDocument ||
  iframe.contentWindow.document;
  const data = iframeDocument.querySelector('.data-point').innerText;
  // Process and use the data in the prototype
};
```

Ensure that API calls are made to fetch real-time data from the identified sources, using methods such as `fetch` or `XMLHttpRequest` to integrate the data into the prototype.

Step 8 - Building Browser Extension: The standard Chrome extension creation process uses a `manifest.json` file to define the extension's properties, permissions, and resources. This file grants the extension necessary permissions, including access to active tabs and the ability to execute scripts (“Extensions / Get started | Chrome for Developers”). When the user clicks on the Chrome browser extension, it initiates the process by injecting a JavaScript path into the existing webpage DOM. This is highlighted as Section A in the accompanying diagram Fig.1.

Step 9 - Injection of JavaScript into the Webpage DOM: The extension injects a script tag into the webpage, which loads a JavaScript file from the local server. This process is illustrated in Section B of the diagram. An example of the script tag injected is: To furnish AI assistance to participants, rudimentary software was constructed utilizing PHP and JQuery, with JSON support for Rest API calls. Following a sample code that loads the JavaScript file from the specified URL and appends it to the document's body, enabling real-time DOM manipulation:

```
fetch('http://localhost:8000/remote-script.js')
  .then(response => response.text())
  .then(scriptText => {
    const script = document.createElement('script');
    script.type = 'text/javascript';
    script.text = scriptText;
    document.body.appendChild(script);
  })
  .catch(error => console.error('Error loading remote
script:', error));
```

Step 10 - Modification of DOM Elements: The injected JavaScript file contains code designed to modify the DOM elements using methods such as `querySelector` and `document.getElementById()`. This allowed for the removal of specific portions of the webpage and the addition of new sections. The functionality extends to creating new page views and navigation elements, enabling users to seamlessly move through these new views. This step is crucial for providing a dynamic and responsive user experience. For example, following is sample DOM from a webpage, which will be updated, where the content in paragraph has to be changed with new content:

Current DOM:

```
<body>
  <div id="content">
    <p>Hello, world!</p>
```

```
    </div>  
  
</body>
```

The basic JavaScript code that would change the paragraph content:

```
var paragraph = document.querySelector('#content p');  
paragraph.textContent = "Text changed dynamically!";
```

When this above script is executed, the following DOM is updated in runtime:

```
<body>  
  <div id="content">  
    <p>Hello, Good morning! </p>  
  </div>  
</body>
```

The above example demonstrates live editing of the DOM using JavaScript selectors.

Step 11 - Scanning and Gathering Data from the DOM: In addition to modifying the DOM, the injected JavaScript also scans the existing DOM to gather data from live page elements such as rendered charts, grid tables, and form fields. The collected data can then be sent to the local server backend for processing. This process ensures that the new or modified DOM elements are populated with relevant, real-time data based on user interaction.

Step 12 - Gathering Data from Live Application APIs (Optional) : In addition to modifying the DOM, the injected JavaScript also leverages live application APIs to fetch real-time data. Instead of scanning the existing DOM for data, the script makes asynchronous API calls to the application's backend to retrieve current data from sources such as databases, external services, and real-time analytics platforms. This data includes dynamically updated information from charts, grid tables, and form fields. The fetched data can then be sent to the local server backend for further processing. This approach ensures that the new or modified DOM elements are populated with accurate, up-to-date information directly from the live APIs, providing a more reliable and interactive user experience that closely mirrors the actual application environment.

Step 13 - Backend Processing and Integration with AI Services: The backend, powered by PHP, Python, or similar languages, processes the data received from the client-side script. It can also query large language models (LLMs), machine learning (ML), or other AI services using JSON or XML-based queries through POST or GET calls. The outcomes from these AI services can be utilized to populate the updated DOM views in the browser, ensuring that the prototype accurately reflects dynamic data and AI-driven features.

By following these steps, it can be ensured that the data is available for prototype to be accurately populated with real-time data, providing a realistic and functional representation of the final product.

3 The Experiment & Post Survey

3.1 Experimental Design and Execution

To analyze the effectiveness of the proposed hypothesis, over a period of 4 months, two advanced prototypes were created using *ProDaLiDE* method. These prototypes were targeting already running one internal legacy web application for supply-chain domain using a third-party platform and another one and one public customer facing SaaS web portal, where some AI features are planned to be integrated, including a responsive chat-bot and some cards populated by AI.

Fig. 3. Lo-fi concepts used to get initial agreement from all stakeholders before moving into the prototyping phase.

Fig. 4. Dynamic prototype created with *ProDaLiDE* approach; the dashed-highlighted area shows the section created using DOM editing in real-time over the existing target web application and using live-data.

For each of the prototype, as per the design process, based on the stakeholder requirements, the designer initially created a high-level, block-level low-fidelity concept using Figma. This preliminary stage involved outlining the essential layout and functional elements of the web application, focusing on user flow and interaction design without delving into detailed aesthetics. Once the stakeholders reviewed and approved the Figma wireframes, the designer transitioned to a more dynamic prototyping phase using *ProDaLiDE* approach.

This approach also helped reducing missing or mismatched data points on the prototyping along with no dead or broken links in both the prototypes (Refer Table 2).

Table 2. Analyzing *ProDaLiDE* prototypes.

Prototype	Prototyping Tool	Data Points (Fields/ labels/ table rows)	Data Mismatch / Missing Data Issues	% of data points impacted	Dead-end/ Broken/ Missing Links	Iterations on Prototype based on stakeholder's feedback
Prototype A	<i>ProDaLiDE</i>	204	0	10.69	0	0
Prototype B	<i>ProDaLiDE</i>	127	0	8.61	0	0

3.2 Post Prototyping Survey & Results

In both the prototypes experiments, at the end a survey was conducted to understand the effectiveness of the approach. The questions included multiple as well as open ended questions. The designers as well as stakeholders took part in the survey making it total 26 participants.

Results of Survey: All 26 participants found this method as a solution can solve some of the key challenges in prototyping for data-driven web-applications. 18 participants (69.23%) felt the ability to quickly use live data to run the prototype without the actual implementation by the platform engineering team is the biggest benefit of this approach. Only 4 participants (15.3%) believed this approach may not work for larger complex data intensive products.

Some Key insights from Survey: From the open-ended question regarding where the participants found this method useful and potential benefits of this approach, some of the key insights we got:

“This approach can help improve in prototyping predictive interfaces, as prediction of nature would depend on the data outcome, and the outcome from AI services vary even for the same scenarios. This approach gives a true picture of how the real product UI might look like in different scenario”

“Now it would be easy to convince the stakeholder, where the earlier approach with mock data struggled to do”

“Can be useful in data analytics platform related projects”

4 Conclusion

From the experiments, it is concluded that *Prototyping with Data-driven Live DOM Editing (ProDaLiDE)* approach of advanced prototyping can significantly help accurately reflect how users will interact with the final product, especially for prototyping data driven views or AI enabled features for web applications.

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